

A STUDY ON THE EFFECTS OF ACADEMIC STRESS ON SENIOR STUDENTS IN COLLEGE

AUTHOR: Dr. Rajasekhar Devarapalli
Associate Professor

DRK COLLEGE OF ENGINEERING & TECHNOLOGY, HYDERABAD, TELANGANA, INDIA

Abstract:

The prime aim of the present study was to study academic stress among senior college students. A total sample comprised of 160 students (male and female of Commerce and Arts stream) from various senior colleges of Kolhapur district, Maharashtra state, India which was selected by randomly. The age range of selected students was 18 to 21 years. An effective tool of academic stress scale prepared by R. Balaji Rao was used for measuring the variables of the study. Finally, obtained data was analyzed by statistical techniques of mean, SD, t test and correlation of coefficient. The result reveals that Commerce and Arts senior college student not differs significantly on academic stress. The result reveals that there is significant interaction between gender and stream in relation to academic stress.

Keywords: Academic Stress, Senior College Students and Commerce and Arts stream.

Introduction:

Today's world called as knowledge as it is world of stress. Today stress is becoming major part of human life. There are lots of stresses in senior college students especially academic stress, family stress, financial stress, examination stress and career related stress etc. The causes of stress in students' life are different such as physical, mental, emotional or social. Some of researchers recommended that stress among college students becoming major issue because of its affects on physiological, psychological health as well as academic performance of students (Struthers et al., 2000 & Misra, et al. 2000). Students have different personalities; so they get different experiences of stress. A lot of student takes high academic stress at the time of preparation of examination and it caused to incompleteness of preparation of study, disrupted timetable, anxiety and fear of examination and finally adverse effect on marks or grade. Some results of the study indicate that there is no significance difference between male and female students on academic stress. Both male and

female student exhibits similar kind of stress in academic field. Stress is also related to unpleasant factors such as change in climate and hormonal changes in adolescence. Byron, brun & Ivers (2008) described some specific factors such as changes in living atmosphere, financial management and difficulties in personal and academic life. Sreeramareddy et al. (2007) indicated that excessive assignment, peer competition, poor social skills these factors also responsible for increasing stress in students. According to psychologist, stress is not only harmful to human being but also it is useful to us. With the help of eustress we can achieve any goal, we can complete our work in proper time and that make to us happy and satisfy.

Impact of Stress on Students:

The following factor suggests negative impact of stress on students.

1. Increasing irritability
2. Fatigue
3. Loss of appetite
4. Disrupted family life and relationship
5. Isolation
6. Inattention
7. Decreasing quality of work
8. Health problem
9. Tendency towards Addiction

But, Stress can be also positive, so the following factor shows positive impact of stress.

1. It can aware or ready to any work.
2. It can improve quality of life.
3. It can make us stronger and creative.
4. It can be make inspiration or provide motivation.

Importance of the study:

Education plays a vital role in human life. Education shapes effectively the behavior of an individual. But, In today's competitive world, students are facing a lot of academic issues such as regularly presence in class, tough-closed timetable, vast syllabuses, busy schedule of examination especially semester pattern, fear of failure and anxiety of future career etc. These issues are creating lot of physiological as well as psychological problems in college students. Increasing in depression, nervousness, frustration or any stress related disorders increasing day by day. In present era, the mental health of students is burning issue and its adverse impact on suicide among students. The decline in mental health is an impact of increasing academic stress in students. The report of Lancer indicates that there is highest suicide rate in India among youth. Students (youth) are prime pillar of our nation; they are innovator and creature of any nation. So, we have to give preference to development of students. That's why, the present research is undertaken. The present work is an attempt to understand and study the academic stress among students. The result of this study will be definitely useful to understand and deal with academic stress among students.

Review related to Study:

1. **Dr. Suresh Prabhu (2019)** conducted a study on academic stress among higher secondary students. A total sample comprised of 250 students of XI standard studying in various higher secondary schools from Namakkal district, Tamil Nadu, India were selected for this study randomly in this study. An effective tool of academic stress scale developed by R. Balaji Rao was applied to data collection. The obtained data was analyzed by using standardized statistical techniques of mean, SD and 't' test. The result found that there is no significance difference between gender, locality, management, subject and parents education in relation to academic stress.
2. **Dr Naveen Prasadula (2020)** studied gender difference in stress among university students. A total sample included of 140 (70 male and 70 female) university post graduate students in L. M. N. U., Darbhanga. Purposive sampling method was adopted for selection of sample in this study. For the assessment of variable, Singh personal stress source inventory (SPSSI) was used for the data collection in this study.

The result of the study reveals that male students possess higher stress than female students.

3. **Reddy et al. (2018)** explored a study on academic stress and its sources among university students. Participants of general pool students involved which was selected using random sampling method in this study. A tool of academic aggressive scale prepared by Rajendran and Kaliappan (1991) was applied for the data collection and standardized statistical techniques such as mean, SD and ANNOVA was adopted for analyze the obtained data. The major finding of the study is gender and stream significantly differs on academic stress.

Statement of the Problem:

To study academic stress among senior college students.

Objectives of the study:

The researcher framed following objectives for the present study.

1. To find out the academic stress level in relation to gender.
2. To find out academic stress level in relation stream
3. To find out the interaction effect between gender and stream in relation to academic stress.

Hypothesis:

The researcher framed following hypothesis for this study.

1. There would be no significant difference between academic stress in relation to gender.
2. There would be no significant difference between academic stress in relation to stream.
3. There would be no interaction effect between gender and stream in relation to academic stress.

Methodology:

1. Sample:

The sample was taken from various senior colleges from Kolhapur city, Maharashtra state, India. A total sample comprised of 160 (40 male and 40 female) senior college students who were studying in arts and commerce stream selected for

this study. Random sampling method was used for the selection of sample in this study. The age range of the selected participants was 18 to 21 years.

Table No. 3.3

Distribution of Sample

Stream ↓ Gender →	Male	Female	Total
Arts	40	40	80
Commerce	40	40	80
Total	80	80	160

2. Variables:

Independent Variable:

1. Gender: Male
Female
2. Stream: Commerce students
Arts students

Dependent Variable: Level of academic stress

3. Tools:

The researcher selected a standardized tool of academic stress scale developed by R. Balaji Rao to investigate the academic stress level of senior college students for data collection.

I) Academic Stress Scale:

This scale is developed by R. Balaji Rao. The scale consists of 40 items with five alternatives such as No stress, Slightly stress, Moderate stress, Highly stress and Extremely high stress. There is no time limit; but it can be complete within 20 to 30 minutes.

The scoring procedure of the scale is showing in the following table.

Table No. 2

Description of Scoring Procedure of the Scale

Nature of Response	Weightage
No Stress	0
Slightly Stress	1
Moderate Stress	2
Highly Stress	3
Extremely High Stress	4

According to manual of this scale, high score indicates high academic stress and low score indicates low academic stress.

4. Research Design:

The researcher employed 2×2 factorial design in this study which is showing in the following table.

Table No. 3

Research design

		Gender (A)	
		Male A1	Female A2
Stream (B)	Commerce B1	A1B1 N = 80	A2B1 N = 80
	Arts B2	A1B2 N = 80	A2B2 N = 80

The experimental groups which employed in above table are as follows;

A1B1 = Male Commerce Students

A1B2 = Male Arts Students

A2B1 = Female Commerce Students

A2B2 = Female Arts Students

5. Statistical Analysis:

The obtained data was analyzed by the using following effective statistical tools.

- Mean
- SD
- Two way ANNOVA

6. Result and Discussion:

Table No. 4

Mean and SD of academic stress in relation to gender

	A1B1 (Male Commerce Students)	A1B2 (Male Arts Students)	A2B1 (Female Commerce Students)	A2B2 (Female Arts Students)
N	160	160	160	160
Mean	43.5	49.2	43.7	45.3
SD	12.9	13.0	12.6	13.9

Figure No. 1

Mean and SD of academic stress in relation to gender

Table No. 1 and Figure No. 1 shows that the mean and SD value of independent variable of gender and stream of academic stress in relation to gender. The independent variables in this study are gender and stream. Mean value of male commerce students on academic stress is 43.5 and SD value is 12.9. Mean value of

male arts students on academic stress is 49.2 and SD value is 13.0. However, mean value of female commerce students on academic stress is 43.7 and SD value is 12.6. Mean value of female arts students on academic stress is 45.3 and SD is 13.9. But it is not possible to draw meaningful conclusions only the basis of mean and SD values. So, the data were treated by using two-way ANNOVA is presented in the table no. 4.2.

Table No. 5

Summary of Two Way ANNOVA for academic stress

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sign.
Gender	129.6	1	129.6	0.74	0.01
Stream	164.02	1	164.02	0.95	0.01
Gender × Stream	525.63	1	525.63	3.03	0.05
Within Sum of Square	27072.65	156	173.54		
Total	27891.9	159			

Significant $P < 0.01 = 6.79$ and $P < 0.05 = 3.87$

Table No. 4.2 shows that the summary of ANOVA for academic stress in relation to gender and stream. First independent variable in the study is a gender. F ratio for the independent variable of gender is ($F = 0.74$, $df 1, 156$, $P > 0.01$). F value is not significant at both level of confidence. The second independent variable in this study is stream. F ratio for the independent variable of stream on academic stress is ($F = 0.95$, $df 1, 156$, $P > 0.01$). F value is significant at both level of confidence. F value is not significant at the both level of confidence. Interaction effect of gender and stream f ratio is ($F = 3.03$, $df 1, 156$, $P > 0.05$). F value is not significant at both level of confidence.

Hypothesis No. 1 There would be no significant difference between academic stress in relation to gender.

Table No. 6

Showing Mean, SD and F value of academic stress in relation to gender

Gender	N	Mean	SD	F	Sign.
Male	80	46.48	13.02	0.74	NS
Female	80	44.46	13.46		

Figure No. 2

Showing mean & SD of academic stress in relation to gender

Above concluded of mean represents that the male students are shows higher academic stress than female students but results of F test represents that no significance difference in gender. It means that hypothesis no. 1; “There would be no significant difference between academic stress in relation to gender.” has not proven. It is cleared and concluded that there is no significance difference between academic stress in relation to gender. This result might be occurred because of male and female student shows similar desire in their subject or stream. Both male and female students may be equally express fear and anxiety, poor time management, pressure of teachers as well as parents, exam stress, tension of results and worry about career etc.

Similar result found that Dr. Suresh Prabhu (2015) studied academic stress among higher secondary students and concluded that there is no significance difference between female and male adolescents in relation to social adequacy.

Another study conducted by Kaur and Kaur (2016) on academic stress in relation to emotional stability of adolescent students and found that no difference

between academic stress among students. Khan and Kausar (2013) also found that there is no significance difference between male and female students in ration to academic stress.

Hypothesis No. 2 There would be no significant difference between academic stress in relation to stream.

Table No. 7

Showing Mean, SD and F value of academic stress in relation to stream

Stream	N	Mean	SD	F	Sign.
Commerce	80	44.40	12.86	0.95	NS
Arts	80	46.55	13.61		

Figure No. 3

Showing mean & SD of academic stress in relation to stream

Above concluded of mean represents that the Commerce students are shows higher academic stress than Arts students but results of F test represents that no significance difference in gender. It means that hypothesis no. 2; “There would be no significant difference between academic stress in relation to stream.” has not proven. It is cleared and concluded that there is no significance difference between academic stress in relation to stream. This result might be occurred because of Commerce and Arts student shows similar desire in their subject or stream. Both Commerce and Arts student may be equally express syllabuses difficulty, competition, tough class load, inadequacy of academic environment, worried about future responsibilities, over workload of semester examination and low level of motivation.

Similar result found that Dr. Suresh Prabhu (2015) studied academic stress among higher secondary students and concluded that there is no significance difference between Science and Arts students in relation to academic stress.

Another finding of the study, Waghachavare et al. conducted a cross-sectional study of stress among junior college students in a rural area and found that there is no significance difference between academic stress and stream. Bataineh (2013) also found that there is no significance difference between specializations in relation to academic stress.

Hypothesis No. 3 There would be no interaction effect between gender and stream in relation to academic stress.

Table No. 8

Showing Mean, SD and F value of interaction effect between gender and stream on academic stress

Factors	N	Mean	SD	F	Sign.
Gender	80	45.47	13.24	3.03	NS
Stream	80	45.45	13.23		

Figure No. 4

Showing interaction effect between gender and stream on academic stress

Above concluded of mean represents that the gender are shows slightly academic stress than stream of students but results of F test represents that no interaction effect (no significance difference) between gender and stream in relation

to stress. It means that hypothesis no. 3; “There would be no interaction effect between gender and stream in relation to academic stress.” has not proven. It is cleared and concluded that there is no interaction effect between gender and stream in relation to academic stress. According to Awing & Agolla (2008) that overcrowded classroom, semester pattern examination, inadequate infrastructures as well as resources, poor library resources and vast syllabuses increases level of stress in both male and female students.

7. Conclusion:

1. Male and female students not differ significantly in relation to academic stress.
2. Commerce and Arts students not differ significantly in relation to academic stress.
3. An interaction effect between gender and stream is not affects significantly to academic stress.

8. Suggestions:

The researcher has suggested some suggestion to students.

1. Always be realistic and think positively.
2. Regular exercise can be helpful to decrease in stress.
3. Create a proper timetable of your work and follow it.
4. Know your strong and weakness sides and try to overcome on it.
5. Maintain interpersonal relationship.
6. Involve in curricular, extra-curricular and extension activities of college.

The researcher also suggested some suggestions to institution.

1. Institution should provide academic facilities to students.
2. Institution should aware about better infrastructure.
3. Institution should implement co-curricular, extra-curricular and extension activities in relation to academic concern.
4. Institution should arrange parent meet in each semester.
5. Institution should focus on career oriented courses for students.

9. References:

1. Agolla, J. E. (2009). Occupational stress among police officers. The case of Bostwana police service, *Res. J. Bus. manage*, vol. 2(1), pp. 25-35.
2. Bataineh, M. Z. (2013). Academic stress among undergraduate students: The case of education faculty of King Saud University. *International Interdisciplinary Journal of Education*. vol. 2(1), pp. 82-88.
3. Jain, G. and Singhai, M. (2017). Academic stress amongst students: A review of literature. *Prestige e-Journal of Management and Research*. vol. 4(2), pp. 58-67.
4. Dr Naveen Prasadula A study on the effects of academic stress on senior students in college.
5. Khan, M. J. and Kausar, H. (2013). Effect of perceived academic stress on students' performance. *FWU Journal of Social Sciences*. vol. 7(2), pp. 146-151.
6. Kumari, S. (2017). A study of gender difference in stress among university students. *International Journal of Research and Analytical Reviews (IJRAR)*. vol. 4(4), pp. 374- 377.
7. Prabhu, S. (2015). A study on academic stress among higher secondary students. *International Journal of Humanities and Social Science Invention*. vol. 4(10), pp. 63-68.
8. Reddy, K. J. and et al. (2018). Academic stress and its sources among university students. *Biomedical & Pharmacology Journal*. vol. 11(1), pp. 531-537.
9. Thakkar, A. (2018). Academic stress in students.